

D1.4 First results from model electrode studies of reversible electrodes delivered to WP3

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Executive summary

We present the results of the first model electrode study, where the geometry-independent relations between polarisation resistance (R_p) of $\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{La}_{0.5}\text{CoO}_{6-\delta}$ (BLC) and T , $p\text{O}_2$ and $p\text{H}_2\text{O}$ have been extracted. The results are used as inputs in a model for quantifying the partial contributions to electrode polarization from oxide ions and protons, and the mediation of polarization by partial transport of electrode holes in a non-faradaic current. The model is fitted to – and exemplified through – a detailed analysis of the R_p of a brush-painted 3x3 mm BLC electrode on a $\text{BaZr}_{0.4}\text{Ce}_{0.4}\text{Y}_{0.2}\text{O}_{2.9}$ (BZCY442) electrolyte. The model may be used as input in higher-level system models, where the efficiency losses under static operation over the cell in electrolysis or fuel-cell mode can be linked to materials-specific parameters for electrode or electrolyte materials. The model may also incorporate lower-level input from atomistic modelling to give predictive power to materials development and tailoring of functional properties relevant for anodic, cathodic or reversible operation. This delivery is a first step towards a full electrochemical model, where the direct relation between dynamic overpotential and current will be given in an analytical solution.

The study is undertaken on a brush-painted 3x3 mm BLC electrode as a pre-study for the upcoming geometry-resolved model electrode study which will reveal the extension of the reaction zone in x, y and z directions under increasing positive and negative DC bias. The large test-matrix give information of rate-determining reaction steps and the activation energies for protons and oxide ions across these steps for an electrode material with low proton- and high electronic conductivity.

Verification of the experimental set-up will form the basis for further electrode characterisation under DC conditions. Impedance characterisation under DC bias is challenging, and the effect of several cell configurations is therefore investigated. We herein report the results of a cell configuration using Pt as counter electrode (CE) with \varnothing 1 cm. We continue with studying the effect of CE area and material, as the counter electrode may be expected to influence the relative transport of protons, oxide ions and electron holes under DC conditions. We will not report on the results of other cell configurations in this document.

The results of the study with Pt CE is that the polarisation resistance at the working electrode in reversible operation (zero bias) is dominated by mass transfer for the anodic oxidation of water at high temperatures, and by mass transfer for the cathodic oxygen reduction at low temperatures.

Contents

1	Introduction.....	4
1.1	Presentation of WINNER	4
1.2	Scope of the deliverable.....	5
2	Experimental and theory.....	5
2.1	Electrode measurements	5
3	Results	7
3.1	Characterisation of polarisation resistance.....	7
3.2	Degradation.....	9
3.3	Modelling.....	10

1 Introduction

1.1 Presentation of WINNER

The WINNER project aims to develop an efficient and durable technology platform based on electrochemical proton conducting ceramic (PCC) cells designed for unlocking a path towards commercially viable production, extraction, purification and compression of hydrogen at small to medium scale. This will be demonstrated in WINNER in three applications: ammonia cracking, dehydrogenation of hydrocarbons, and reversible steam electrolysis. By such, WINNER will create innovative solutions for flexible, secure and profitable storage and utilization of energy in the form of hydrogen and green ammonia, electrification of the chemical industry and sectors coupling.

The WINNER project builds on the pioneering multidisciplinary expertise of world leading partners in the fields of proton conducting ceramic (PCC) materials and technologies to combine materials science, multi-scale multi-physics modelling and advanced in-situ and operando characterisation methods to unveil unprecedented performance of tubular PCC cells assembled in a flexible multi-tube module operating at industrially relevant conditions. WINNER will develop innovative cell architectures with multifunctional electrodes and a novel pressure-less current collection system using eco-friendly and scalable manufacturing routes.

Figure 1 WINNER concept focusing on novel materials, electrodes, current collection, and assemblies for three main applications.

The experimental activities will be steered by a novel multi-scale multi-physics modelling platform and enhanced experimentation methodologies. These tools combined with advanced operando and in situ methods will serve at establishing correlations between performance and degradation mechanisms associated with both materials properties and interface's evolution upon operation. Testing of cells and modules will also be conducted to define performance and durability in various operation modes. Techno-economic assessment of the novel PCC processes will be conducted as well as Life Cycle Assessment. The project is coordinated by SINTEF with support from University of

Oslo, Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior De Investigaciones Cientificas (CSIC-ITQ), Danmarks Tekniske Universitet (DTU), Aktiebolaget Sandvik Materials Technology, CoorsTek Membrane Sciences AS, ENGIE, Shell Global Solutions International B.V.

1.2 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable reports on model electrode studies for an electrode material with low proton- and high electronic conductivity. Part of the work is dedicated to verify the experimental set-up and understand the influences of geometry and materials under DC conditions. Moreover, the results are utilised to extract parameters for partial contributions from electron holes, oxide ions and protons to the electrolyte and electrode resistance. The deliverable also reports on the model used to describe current voltage (IV) relations over electrode and electrolyte, here exemplified for an oxide electrode with mainly electronic conductivity. The model is designed for incorporating parameters from atomistic modelling and also for implementation in a larger multi-scale model. The results of this deliverable – especially the modelling results – are preliminary and valid for this experimental configuration only, but are nonetheless transferred to WP3 for model integration. The model will also work as a starting point for the upcoming continuation of the model electrode studies, where model electrodes of higher geometrical resolution will be studied to parameterize the extension of the reaction zone (x, y, z) and the (possible) dependency of polarization resistance on applied potential. The first manuscript is drafted based on the initial WP1 results.

2 Experimental and theory

2.1 Electrode measurements

Figure 2: Camera picture of Brush-painted 3x3 mm $Ba_{0.5}La_{0.5}CoO_{6-\delta}$ (BLC) electrodes (4 shown on the left picture) coated on $BaZr_{0.4}Ce_{0.4}Y_{0.2}O_{2.9}$ electrolyte, and SEM micrographs with various magnifications of the electrode.

A 3x3 mm brush-painted model electrode delivered from WP2 (D2.3, Figure 2) was measured in a three-point / 4-wire set-up in a ProboStat™ measurement cell with the working electrode on the top connected to high current and working sense connections, and both reference and counter electrodes on the bottom. The counter electrode was a 0.78 cm² Pt electrode and the reference electrode was a painted Pt ring at the bottom circumference. The current collection on the working electrode was Au-paint annealed in-situ at 650°C prior to the electrode measurements. Performance of the half-cell was measured by Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) with a Zivelab SP2 Potentiostat/Galvanostat under zero bias, and under potentiostatic bias, where the working electrode

was kept at ± 100 mV bias relative to the reference electrode. Prior to each measurement, the cell was kept under the relevant potentiostatic bias for ten minutes, while monitoring the current relaxation and ensuring static DC current during EIS measurements under bias. The EIS measurements were taken in a frequency range from 200 kHz to 500 μ Hz and with 10mV oscillation voltage.

The impedance results were analysed in anodic (100 mV bias), cathodic (-100 mV bias) and reversible (zero bias) operation. Deconvolutions were done with the ZView program (Scribner) and deconvoluted with an equivalent circuit model as presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Equivalent circuit model.

The combination R1/CPE1 was assigned to ohmic resistance and attributed to electrolyte resistance. R2/CPE2 was attributed to the small contribution to resistance and capacitance from the charge transfer reaction at the electrolyte / electrode interface. R3/CPE3 is reported as the middle frequency $R_{p,mf} / C_{mf}$ response, while the sum of R4/CPE4 and G is reported as the low frequency $R_{p,lf} / C_{lf}$.

The partial contributions to R_p from oxide ions, protons and electron holes was found by a multi-step fitting process, as described in detail in a previous work [1] and further developed here. The model relies on the fact that both the electrolyte and the electrode facilitate transport of protons, oxide ions and electron holes, depending on temperature, p_{H_2O} and p_{O_2} . A simple schematic, including the first fitting step of partial conductivities of protons, oxide ions and electron holes is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Schetch of ionic and electronic rails with electrolyte and electrode resistances. First fitting step for electrolyte partial transport versus temperature at zero bias, p_{H_2O} 0.027 atm, and p_{O_2} 3×10^{-5} and 0.2 atm.

The first fitting step establishes partial electrolyte volume resistances ($R_{v,i}$) fittede to R1, according to equation 1:

$$R_v = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{R_{v,h^+}} + \frac{1}{R_{v,H^+}} + \frac{1}{R_{v,O^{2-}}}} \quad (1)$$

with separate conductivity expressions for each $R_{v,i}$, where $\sigma_i = \frac{1}{R_{v,i}}$ and input values for hydration thermodynamics is obtained from separate measurements.[2] In the second fitting step, partial resistances for protons and oxide ions are fitted to rate expressions

$$\frac{1}{R_{p,i}} = nFpO_2^n pH_2O^m A_i^0 \exp\left(-\frac{E_{A,i}}{RT}\right) \quad (2)$$

where dependencies on pH_2O and pO_2 is fixed and pre-exponential values and activation energies are extracted by fitting eq 2 for $R_{p,mf,O^{2-}}$ and R_{p,mf,H^+} to the measured $R_{p,mf}$ according to

$$R_v + R_{p,mf} = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{R_{v,h^+}} + \frac{1}{R_{v,H^+} + R_{p,mf,H^+}} + \frac{1}{R_{v,O^{2-}} + R_{p,mf,O^{2-}}}} \quad (3)$$

Finally, having fixed values for R_v and $R_{p,mf}$, the low frequency response is fitted with individual rate equations to the total DC resistance, according to

$$R_{DC} = R_v + R_{p,mf} + R_{p,lf} = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{R_{v,h^+}} + \frac{1}{R_{v,H^+} + R_{p,mf,H^+} + R_{p,lf,H^+}} + \frac{1}{R_{v,O^{2-}} + R_{p,mf,O^{2-}} + R_{p,lf,O^{2-}}}} \quad (4)$$

Using the individual contributions to R_{DC} , partial currents for oxide ions and protons – along with the non-faradaic current of electron holes – can be extracted under positive and negative DC potential.

3 Results

3.1 Characterisation of polarisation resistance

Impedance sweeps for the BLC electrode are shown in Figure 5 for positive and negative bias at 650°C in wet air, highlighting the discrete contributions at middle- and low frequencies, along with the minor contribution from charge transfer. The data are deconvoluted according to the equivalent circuit shown in Figure 3, and it can be seen that the low frequency response has two contributions, most clearly seen under anodic bias (left). These two contributions – deconvoluted with R4/CPE4 and G – are added together and presented as $R_{p,lf,i}$ for each charge carrier, i .

Figure 5: Nyquist plots of BLC at 650°C in wet air for positive (left) and negative (right) bias.

The total R_p in anodic, cathodic and reversible operation in pO_2 0.2 atm and pH_2O 0.026 atm vs T is presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Polarisation resistance of BLC at pO_2 0.2 atm and pH_2O 0.026 atm vs T under 100 mV anodic bias (blue), -100 mV cathodic bias (red) and zero bias (green).

It can be seen from Figure 6 that while R_p is lower for cathodic operation at high T, it is lower for anodic operation at low T. This result indicates that BLC favours oxygen reduction over water oxidation under

typical operating conditions. Moreover, the ohmic resistance under positive and negative bias – converted to conductivity in Figure 4 – shows that contribution from non-faradaic p-type current is more severe in cathodic operation. Hence, the effect of compliance voltage under bias may influence the measured polarisation. Additional measurements are initiated to study the effect of the experimental setup and selectivity of the counter electrode. The results of separate measurements also indicate that the polarisation resistance – and hence the overpotential – associated with a BLC electrode on a mainly proton conducting electrolyte is not significantly diminished under DC bias up to ± 100 mV. This result is important for the further development of a current-potential model, where a traditional IV relation can be described by a Butler-Volmer formalism, expressing an exponential IV-relation. The results rather suggest a linear IV relation, where the polarisation resistance of a diffusion-limited system is potential-independent.

3.2 Degradation

The BLC electrode showed a significant degradation during the measurements. This degradation was affecting only anodic operation. Impedance sweeps at 650°C in wet air taken 13.08.22, 26.08.22 and 17.11.22 are shown in Figure 7 a and b for 100 mV anodic and cathodic bias, respectively.

Figure 7: Impedance sweeps in anodic (a) and cathodic (b) bias at 650°C in wet air over three months.

The results presented in Figure 5 are taken after 13 days of measuring (26.08. in Figure 7), and the results presented in Figure 6 are taken from low to high T at the end of the measurements period after two to three months of measurements (13.10-24.11). The anodic polarisation is gradually increased from being only slightly higher than the cathodic in the first measurements to becoming around four times higher after three months. In Figure 8 we show the impedance sweeps under 50 mV positive and negative bias for as-prepared electrodes taken 13.08.22 after just one day of measurements. This degradation process weakens the analysis of the data, and the modelling of partial R_p 's shown below is based on a surface partly deactivated for the anodic half-reaction.

Figure 8: Impedance sweeps for a prepared BLC electrode under 50 mV anodic and cathodic bias at 650° in wet air.

3.3 Modelling

The output of the impedance measurements has been used to extract parameters for partial resistances for protons, oxide ions and electron holes over electrolyte and electrode. The fitting of partial electrolyte resistances is shown in Figure 4, and these values are confirmed by plotting the electrolyte volume conductivities versus p_{H_2O} (Figure 9) and fitting Eq 1 to the measured data.

Figure 9: Electrolyte conductivity vs p_{H_2O} at 650°C in air.

The results from the electrolyte modelling vs p_{H_2O} at 650°C and p_{O_2} 0.2 atm show that the electrolyte is dominated by proton transport at the highest p_{H_2O} , and by electron holes in drier conditions. The transport of oxygen vacancies is lower, but significant, and becomes the dominant ionic charge carrier

in dry conditions. Hence, with a thick electrolyte – where R_v takes the larger part of R_{DC} – the current will be dominated by electron holes and protons in wet conditions. If, however, the electrolyte is thin, R_v takes a smaller part of R_{DC} , and the electrode is selective for oxide ions rather than protons, oxide ions may dominate over protons and electron holes in the DC current even in relatively wet conditions.

The fitting of $R_{p,mf}$ and $R_{p,lf}$ to eq's 1-4 is shown in Figure 10 for anodic (a, c) and cathodic (b, d) operation. In the figure, open black squares are deconvoluted results, dotted lines are partial R_p 's for protons (blue) and oxide ions (red), while solid black line is modelled $R_{p,mf}$ and $R_{p,mf}$ partially short circuited by p-type conductivity.

Figure 10: BLC: $R_{p,mf}$ and $R_{p,lf}$ modelled for protons and oxide ions in anodic (a and c) and cathodic (b and d) bias in wet air.

The results show that the BLC electrode is selective for oxide ions at high temperatures and low p_{H_2O} and for protons at low temperatures and high p_{H_2O} . This is due to the lower R_{p,lf,O_2} at high temperature and R_{p,lf,H^+} at low temperature, and holds for both anodic and cathodic operation. This trend is reflected by the higher activation energy for oxide ions than protons over the low frequency mass transfer reaction step. The lower modelled activation energy for the protonic low frequency reaction may also be an effect of some solubility of protons in BLC at these temperatures.

In Figure 11, we show dependencies of $R_{p,mf}$ and $R_{p,lf}$ on p_{H_2O} under anodic and cathodic bias at 650°C in p_{O_2} 0.2 atm, resolved in contributions from protons and oxide ions.

Figure 11: $R_{p,mf}$ and $R_{p,lf}$ under anodic (a and c) and cathodic (b and d) bias at 650°C in pO_2 0.2 atm vs pH_2O fitted to eq's 1-4 for mf and lf, respectively. Red and blue dashed lines are partial R_p 's for oxide ions and protons, respectively.

The results show an increase in both $R_{p,mf}$ and $R_{p,lf}$ with increasing pH_2O under anodic bias. The results are fitted to eq (1-4), giving overall m -values as listed in Table 3. The pH_2O -dependency of $R_{p,mf}$ in anodic operation is, however, not linear in the log-log plot, suggesting that this process is not well fitted with a kinetic rate-expression (eq 2), but should rather be fitted to a diffusion expression (eq 5), where the flux reaches a maximum at a surface coverage (θ) of 0.5.

$$j_i = nFD_i c \theta (1 - \theta) \left(-\frac{\Delta\mu_i}{x} \right) \quad (5)$$

Eq. 5 gives the diffusion j of charge carrier i with a diffusion constant D , concentration of diffusion sites, c , in a chemical gradient $\Delta\mu_i$ over the distance x . We have not evaluated this expression at this stage, and the results will be implemented in the IV model when it is further verified.

The series connected resistances in each charge carrier rail give total $R(DC)$ for protons and oxide ions and can be used to evaluate the partial currents of protons and oxide ions, as exemplified for anodic operation in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Left: DC resistance for protons (blue solid line) and oxide ions (red solid line) and fraction of PCE (blue dashed line) vs SOE (red dashed line) versus T in anodic operation at $p_{O_2} = 0.2$ atm and $p_{H_2O} = 0.026$ atm. Middle: Transition region from PCE to SOE vs electrolyte thickness at $p_{H_2O} 0.026$ atm. Right: Transition region from PCE to SOE vs electrolyte thickness at $p_{H_2O} 0.5$ atm.

The partial currents can be calculated for different thicknesses of the electrolyte (middle) and for higher p_{H_2O} (right), showing that at low p_{H_2O} , a thin electrolyte and high temperatures favour oxygen transport, and that a thick electrolyte and low temperatures favour proton transport. At high p_{H_2O} (0.5 atm), the positive m -values (p_{H_2O} dependencies of the reaction rates) for the R_p 's in the protonic rail and the negative m -values for the R_p 's in the oxide ion rail favours PCE operation at all relevant temperatures. We have excluded the non-faradaic current from the figures, but the model may also evaluate faradaic efficiency as a function of operation conditions.

In Table 1 to 3, we give preliminary extracted values from the fitting of the impedance data to equations (1-4).

Table 1: Pre-exponential factors and activation energies in 100 mV anodic bias according to equation (2-4).

	A^0 (for 1/R)	E_a (kJ/mol)
R_{p,mf,H^+}	2000	65
$R_{p,mf,O^{2-}}$	400	80
R_{p,lf,H^+}	2	30
$R_{p,lf,O^{2-}}$	2	65

Table 2: Pre-exponential factors and activation energies in -100 mV cathodic bias according to equation (1-4).

	A^0 (for 1/R)	E_a (kJ/mol)
R_{p,mf,H^+}	35000	75

$R_{p,mf}, O^{2-}$	80000	100
$R_{p,lf}, H^+$	40000	80
$R_{p,lf}, O^{2-}$	3E+08	150

The trend in Table 1 and 2 is that while the pre-exponential values are similar or higher for the protonic rail in anodic bias, they many orders of magnitude higher for the $R_{p,lf}$ in the oxide ionic rail. This large difference in cathodic operation may reflect that the electrode's partial ionic conductivities allows oxide ions to react all over the electrode surface, while the reactions in the protonic rail is confined to a smaller area around the triple phase boundary. The second trend is that the R_p 's in the oxide ion rail has a higher activation energy than the R_p 's in the protonic rail. The coupling between proton transfer in and on the electrode is expected to have a lower activation energy, while the same processes for oxide ions are typically associated with higher activation energies.[3] The last trend is that the cathodic reactions in the protonic rail is associated with higher activation energies (75 and 80 kJ/mol for $R_{p,mf}$ and $R_{p,lf}$, respectively) than the anodic (65 and 30 kJ/mol for $R_{p,mf}$ and $R_{p,lf}$, respectively). This trend may reflect the difference in the material's ability to reduce oxygen molecules relative to oxidising water molecules. The low activation energy for R_p 's in the protonic rail will partly reflect a gradual increase in the reaction zone as the electrode material dissolves more protons at lower temperatures. We have chosen to neglect this at the present state and use the standard Arrhenius' behaviour with constant reaction zone over the whole temperature region.

In Table 3 we give preliminary values for n and m (according to eq 2) for $R_{p,mf}$ and $R_{p,lf}$ in anodic and cathodic operation, showing the dependency of each partial R_p on the activity of oxygen and water.

Table 3: n and m values (according to Eq. 2) for R_p 's in the protonic and oxide ionic rails at 650°C under anodic and cathodic operation

		Mf		Lf	
		n	m	n	m
Anodic	H+	-0.25	0.25	-0.5	0.25
	O2-	-0.25	-0.5	-0.5	-1
Cathodic	H+	0.25	0.25	0.5	0.5
	O2-	0.25	-0.25	0.5	0

The results in Table 3 will be used to evaluate the nature of the reaction steps giving rise to $R_{p,mf}$ and $R_{p,lf}$. A preliminary interpretation is that $R_{p,mf}$ reflects a diffusion process in or on the electrode, while $R_{p,lf}$ arises from an adsorption/desorption or dissociation/association step.

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